

STRADDLING SUPERPOWERS: PAKISTAN'S STRATEGIC BALANCING
AMID US-CHINA RIVALRY

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Abstract

This research paper examines how Pakistan's foreign policy toward its neighbors, primarily India, Afghanistan, and Iran is changing due to the increasing competition between the US and China. The study indicates that US-China relations involve complex aspects of political, economic, and military cooperation with Pakistan located at the crossroads of the world's two largest powers. This research highlights Pakistan's effort to strike a careful balance between its traditional association with the US and its growing cooperation with China, as illustrated by CPEC. This study also looks at Pakistan's weakening relationship with its neighbors, highlighting the tense relations with Iran, the growing hostilities with India after Jammu and Kashmir's special status was revoked, and the unstable circumstances in Afghanistan. In doing so, this paper sheds light on the complex geopolitical context pertinent to the current paper's issue, the understanding of which is highly critical for policymakers, academicians, and other stakeholders interested in analyzing the evolution of global power and its implications for regional stability and economic partnership. This research article also makes a meaningful conclusion to summarize the entire discussion.

INTRODUCTION

The US-China competition has developed into a significant framework that influences discussions and choices about international politics, military strategy, the economy, and the military in recent years. The "War on Terror" was previously widely supported, but now this rivalry has supplanted it as the primary lens through which most international news is viewed and comprehended. The 21st century is a time of competition between the US and China and this competition is more intense because of issues with

economic, military, ideological, and digitization.¹..With Pakistan positioned as a key component in this new superpower rivalry, the growth of China as a global force is threatening the US-led global hegemony and causing an enormous power shift in the international order. Pakistan is under pressure to align with one of the major power blocs, especially from the US, amidst increased global tensions similar to the Cold War era. Pakistan, alternatively, is bucking this trend to maintain a

¹. Graeme Thompson, "Globalization, Geopolitics, and the U.S.-China Rivalry after Covid-19," Journal of Applied History, 2021.

balanced foreign policy. It seeks to keep its long-standing ties with China while also pursuing good relations with all nations. During his interview with China Global Television Network (CGTN), Head of State Imran Khan suggested that Pakistan would not be altering its relationship with a reliable partner.² Pakistan affirmed its close connection with China in a letter to the World Political Parties Summit on July 6, 2021, referring to the two countries as "iron brothers." Pakistan supported China's efforts to uphold international order, advance global development, and promote peace. The statement was further praised by President Xi Jinping for strengthening his position as a world leader and dramatically boosting global sustainable progress through the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI).³ This could be Pakistan's way of responding to US pressure to break its ties to the rising powerhouse.

A complex combination of extremism, transnational threats, and frailer, minor states make up Asia's geopolitical landscape. These issues are complemented by China's ascent and growing multipolarity, which poses a challenge to US dominance. This dynamic region, which embodies the complexity of the new Cold War, also acts as a testing ground for crossing security concerns spanning from classic and realism geopolitics to contemporary globalized security dilemmas. It is believed that the drawing of Washington and NATO from Kabul in September 2021 will worsen regional instability and escalate the competition for supremacy between Beijing and Washington in South Asia. This change in strategy not only increases tensions within the region but also highlights India's geopolitical status to the United States as a counterweight to China.

Concurrently, after years of focusing on counterterrorism, the United States is shifting its military priority to opposing China and Russia.⁴

Several outstanding concerns have underwritten the slow decline of relations between Islamabad and its neighbors. Relations between Pakistan and Iran have deteriorated due to the cancellation of a gas pipeline project, border disputes with Iran, and Iran's closer connections with India as a result of projects like the Chabahar Port. Pakistan's ties with India have reached a low point, which has been made worse by India's suspension of Jammu and Kashmir's special position in August 2019, which has increased tensions along the Line of Control. Meanwhile, the ongoing upheaval in Afghanistan continues to have a detrimental influence on Pakistan.⁵ In August 2019, Pakistan's special status for Jammu and Kashmir was reversed, which led to increased tensions with India. Pakistan also confronts significant internal and external issues, such as economic instability and high debt. One important economic lifeline is thought to be the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC). At the same time, changes are seen in Pakistan's foreign policy dynamics, particularly in light of the country's growing links to China and Western worries over Pakistan's position on Kashmir and possible shifts in foreign policy.⁶

RESEARCH QUESTIONS:

1. How does US-China competition influence Pakistan's policy towards neighboring countries India, Afghanistan, and Iran?
2. How has Pakistan's foreign policy evolved in response to the rivalry between the US and China?

² Umar Karim, "Pakistan's foreign policy approach: Balancing among global stakeholders," Arab News, [Online].

Available: <https://www.arabnews.pk/node/2108006>

³ "Pakistan supports China's efforts to safeguard world peace, contribute to global development: PM Imran," Dawn, July 6, 2021. <https://www.dawn.com/news/1633560>.

⁴ Baqai, H. N. S. (2022). A rearticulation of Pakistan's foreign policy in the wake of the twenty-first century challenges. *Global Pakistan: Pakistan's Role in The International System*, 171-194.

https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=A+rearticulation+of+Pakistan%E2%80%99s+foreign+policy+in+the+wake+of+the+twenty-first+century+challenges.

⁵ Aljazeera. (2019, August 9). Pakistan's relations with neighbors deteriorate. <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2019/8/9/pakistans-relations-with-neighbours-deteriorate>

⁶ Darabu, Fauzia, and Sayeda Daud. "New Era in Pakistan's Foreign Policy: Problems and Prospects." *Pakistan Journal of International Affairs* 4, no. 1 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.52337/pjia.v4i1.38>

METHODOLOGY:

This paper presents an in-depth analysis of descriptive research. The researcher has benefited from descriptive research in identifying and comprehending potential causes that served as the basis for Pakistan's change in foreign policy. Both primary and secondary sources have been used for this paper. Primary Sources: The books have helped assemble the historical context of Pakistan's foreign policy framework. These publications have helped identify the facts and events that forced Pakistan to alter its foreign policy, particularly in the wake of the 9/11 tragedy. Some articles from reputable publications and journals as well as current reports from some of the correspondents of well-known TV shows and newspapers are examples of secondary sources. This has helped the subject because it helped in strengthening the opinion of the researcher.

Significance of the study:

In considering the proposals of the US-China rivalry on Pakistan's foreign policy towards the regional states, the study presents assess of the global superpower's dynamics hence, influencing regional alliances and conflicts. Pakistan is situated at the junction of South Asia, Central Asia, and the Middle East thus creating critical aspects of all three spheres of power influence and authority. Moreover, China's influence through the BRI, particularly the CPEC Corridor, and the United States' strategic interests within the regions have significant effects on the countries' diplomatic and economic engagements. Understanding such critical impact is necessary for policymakers, as well as scholars, and regional stakeholders in analyzing broader geopolitical changes that affect regional stability, economic dimensions, and other aspects of countries' strategic decision-making process.

Theoretical framework:

Examining Pakistan's foreign policy toward regional states via the analytical lenses of constructivism and neorealism within the context of the struggle between Beijing and Washington might yield a comprehensive picture of international relations. These two theories offer divergent viewpoints on how states perceive their connections and security, which clarifies Pakistan's strategies and decisions. Constructivism is used to

examine how Pakistan's national identity, social norms, and international roles influence its foreign policy, particularly when it comes to Afghanistan, Iran, and India in the context of the US-China relationship. Constructivists emphasize how common norms, ideas, cultural context, and historical narratives shape state behavior. Pakistan views itself as a nation that stands up for and defends Muslims. Islam has been central to Pakistani identity formation since the country's founding in 1947. This philosophy helped Pakistan win its independence from India. An important factor in shaping Pakistan's political and national character has been General Zia UL Haqq. This influences how it approaches Afghanistan, especially in light of the sizeable Pashto population living on the other side of the border.

Its historical account of providing shelter and support to Afghan mujahideen during the Soviet-Afghan war continues to shape its policies and perception of its place in Afghan politics. It is possible to see Pakistan's backing of the Taliban in Afghanistan as a premeditated attempt to undermine India's might and provide strategic depth in the event of an Indian-Pakistani conflict. Neo-realism emphasizes the organization of the international system and the allocation of power among the states.

Neorealism explains Pakistan's foreign policy toward India: power balancing. By strengthening its armed forces, which include nuclear weapons, and establishing alliances, most notably with China, Pakistan seeks to balance the power of India. In addition to being an issue of power, Pakistan's antagonistic attitude toward India has its roots in historical, theological, and cultural narratives. The Kashmir issue is a tragic example of how identity and historical tensions shape policy agendas.

The strengthening of relations with China through programs like the (CPEC) could be interpreted as an effort to offset the strategic alliance between the US and India, which Pakistan perceives as a threat. Neo-realism interprets this collaboration as a try to alter the balance of power in the area to Pakistan's advantage. The US and Pakistan have a sensible, well-rounded alliance. Pakistan has relied on US economic and military support, but it has also been cautious about US ties to Afghanistan and India. This balancing act is a basic realist strategy to maximize security in a multi-polar world.

Literature review:

The competition between the US and China is increasing on a global scale. This competition primarily occurs in the Indo-Pacific region of Southeast Asia. Both countries have a comparative advantage while Beginning strengths are mostly on the economic and diplomatic side and the US is many-sided. The US raised its profile in Southeast Asia at the tenure of Barack Obama, China has also increased its influence and presence. The United States continues to enjoy significant advantages, even in despite the possibility that China is gaining the advantage. The US needs to stay involved in the region to keep China from overtaking the position. The livery between these countries was not as intense as it is now, tensions may be managed and competitive coexistence can be practiced.⁷ When I use the span "rivalry," I mean a tense association between two countries characterized by long-standing rivalry and hostility that is demonstrated in several confrontations, continuing differences in policy, and the possibility of using force. The rivalry between the US and China is based on prolonged disputes and conflicts. The main issue of dispute between the US and China is in the South China Sea and this dispute intensifies the tensions between these countries, even though they are different from other potential flashpoints like the Korean Peninsula or the Taiwan Strait.⁸ Both countries USA and China compete with each other especially in Asia to become a global hegemon. The rise of China in economics, military as well as in geopolitical aims has had a great impact on international politics and the economy. Experts are worrying about the future hostilities between these two countries particularly in East Asia.⁹

Authorized diplomatic relations were recognized between Beijing and Washington in the early 1970s, simultaneous with China's embrace of Deng Xiaoping's revolutionary program of "reform and opening up." despite the frequent issues, the relationship between the two nations greatly developed and extended during the next forty years. In the nearly forty years that followed, China's links to the US and an international order led and supported by the US expanded in several ways, and relations between the two countries remained generally positive. The United States and China's security relationship moved away from the delay effects of historical wars like the Korean and Vietnam Wars, as well as Maoist China's aid to leftist forces. The common interest of both countries was against the Soviet Union in the 1990s which brought the two countries closer and shifted to chance for US-China collaboration. Clinton's administration viewed China as a strategic ally they did not have any security threats from China. Although Clinton's administration took a measurable step to strengthen US ties in Asia in response to China's rise.¹⁰

The relationship between Beijing and Washington has gotten worse during the tenure of Xi Jinping. China's policy is more assertive and proactive in today's world. So, the USA perceives Beijing as a Geostrategic competitor, a strategic competitor, and a danger to the international system that was created and maintained.¹¹ The tension between the US and China is increasing with each passing day in the current situation. Both countries influence the regional countries for their benefit, and South Asia is not an exception.¹²

⁷ (Shambaugh 2018)U.S.-China Rivalry in Southeast Asia: Power Shift or Competitive Coexistence? *International Security* (2018) 42 (4): 85-127.: https://doi.org/10.1162/isec_a_00314

⁸ *Political Science Quarterly*, Volume 133, Issue 2, Summer 2018, Pages 199-224, <https://doi.org/10.1002/polq.12772>

⁹ Vasil Modebadze, "US-CHINA RIVALRY FOR GLOBAL HEGEMONY," *Journal of Liberty and International Affairs* 6, no. 2 (June 2020): 167-173, accessed May 10, 2024, <https://e-jlia.com/index.php/jlia/article/view/201>.

¹⁰ J deLisle, A Goldstein. *Rivalry and security in a new era for US-China relations*. 2021 - <http://.brookings.edu>

¹¹ J Delisle, A Goldstein. *Rivalry and security in a new era for US-China relations*. 2021 -<http://.brookings.edu>

¹² *Comparative Study of the US and China's Policies towards South Asia in the 21st Century: Implications for Pakistan...* *Global Foreign Policies Review* 3 (2022): L: [http://dx.doi.org/10.31703/gfpr.2022\(V-III\).02](http://dx.doi.org/10.31703/gfpr.2022(V-III).02)

before the researcher discusses the consequences of the Beijing and Washington competition for Pakistan, it is significant to see the different aspects of Pakistani dealings with both countries. After the creation of Pakistan in 1947, Pakistan had a security concern with India and made alliances with the US. During the Cold War, this relationship was mutually beneficial for both countries. The US sees Pakistan as its strategic partner. The closeness of Pakistan with the Soviet Union at that time has an interest for the US. Pakistan joined alliances like CENTO and SEATO to strengthen its security collaboration with the US and UK. Pakistan provided military and economic support through these alliances. But they were unable to keep Pakistan safe throughout its two wars with India, in 1965 and 1971. As a result, Pakistan withdrew from CETO and SENTO in 1971. The geopolitical circumstances of Pakistan changed drastically across several eras, including the post-9/11 era and Afghan - soviet war. During Afghan- soviet war, Pakistan cooperated with the US and in return received assistance from the US. During the war on terror, Pakistan faced a lot of challenges like sanctions and mutual mistrust. Regardless of all the military help from the US, they had disagreements, especially about efforts against the Afghan Taliban. Although Pakistan played a role in the Afghan peace process to mend its relationship with the US, it was all in vain and their relations remained strained. The relationship between China and Pakistan is unique and termed as iron brothers and all-weather friends. Since both countries share a border and have a long-standing rivalry with India. Some researcher argues that the firm relationship with China has depended as a result of the decline in its relations with the West, particularly over the past ten years. China is coming to fill the gap left by the West in Pakistan. China wanted Pakistan to view it as a friendly country even when Mao Zedong was in control, so it constructed its foreign policy toward Pakistan in a way that led

Pakistan's authorities to friend view China as a close ally.¹³

China provides Pakistan with supplies, cash, and arms that it finds difficult to obtain from other sources. Pakistan depends on China in several ways. It shows that China has a significant impact on domestic politics, technology, the economy, and foreign policy. Also, China supported Pakistan on the international forums and used veto power in the UN Security Council. Through this action, China received criticism from the world.¹⁴

Pakistan wants to have a good relationship with Washington and Beijing but faces challenges due to Beijing's growing influence, particularly through the investment in the CPEC. The geopolitical rivalry between the US and China complicated Pakistan's efforts. As a result, Trump has imposed trade disagreements and tariffs on China which has intensified the relations between US and China. These circumstances made it difficult for Pakistan's diplomatic position in the growing tension between these states. Pakistan stands firmly with China when the US criticizes China on different matters, such as human violations in Xinjiang, and supports Beijing's stance on this issue. On the Kashmir issue, China also supported Pakistan. Pakistan believes that China is its reliable ally. Further, the relations between Pakistan's Gulf countries are not good, which pushes Pakistan to have a good relationship with China. Due to the geopolitical challenges faced by Pakistan, China provides both economic and strategic assistance.¹⁵

The rising geopolitical contention between Beijing and Washington is influencing the foreign policy of India and Pakistan, two neighboring countries in South Asia. In this context, China is fortifying its Economic and strategic ties with Islamabad, especially through initiatives related to the BRI, while the United States is forging a tighter partnership with India by offering cutting-edge technologies to assist in modernizing its military. Aiming to control and lessen regional tensions, these developments have created a

¹³ The China-Pakistan Axis: Asia's New Geopolitics (Oxford University Press, 2015), 45-50. Small, The China-Pakistan Axis, 60-65.

¹⁴ Political Science Quarterly, Volume 133, Issue 2, Summer 2018, Pages 199-224, <https://doi.org/10.1002/polq.12772>

¹⁵ U.S.-China Rivalry in Southeast Asia: Power Shift or Competitive Coexistence? International Security (2018) 42 (4): 85-127.

https://doi.org/10.1162/isec_a_00314

strategic quadrilateral comprising Pakistan, China, India, and the United States. Although neither China nor the United States wish to see hostilities worsen, their rivalry may inadvertently lead to more tensions between Pakistan and India. On the other hand, any reduction in hostilities between Beijing and Washington may serve to relieve the strain between Pakistan and India. In this geopolitical context, this complex situation presents India and Pakistan with both opportunities and hazards.¹⁶

Research gap:

While numerous researchers have extensively explored various aspects of US-China rivalry and its impact on Pakistan's policy, there is a specific inquiry gap that the scholar wants to address. My research not only delves into the impact of the US-China rivalry and its consequence on Pakistan's foreign policy but also the broader regional dynamics. My research takes a comprehensive approach by examining the impact of Pakistan's policy towards Afghanistan, India, and Iran, unlike many existing studies that tend to narrow their focus, my research aims to provide a holistic perspective on the multifaceted relationship between US-China, and its impact on Pakistan's policy towards India Afghanistan and Iran.

US China's competition influences Pakistan's policy towards neighboring countries:

The rising geopolitical enmity between Beijing and Washington is making conflict more likely everywhere and in particular areas like South Asia and the Indian Ocean Region (IOR). This competition is like a modern-day Thucydides trap, driven by fast-moving technology, globalized economies, and a complex nuclear environment—factors that reduce the chance of large-scale war but raise the possibility of smaller-scale conflicts and greater strategic unpredictability. In particular, India and Pakistan are heavily impacted by this tension, which forces them to align their military

and nuclear capacities with their respective alliances with Beijing and Washington. These changes in the balance of power in the world. Due to significant projects like China's Belt and Road Initiative (CPEC) and the United States' strategic pivot toward Asia, which are essential in defining the regional power dynamics and overall stability, South Asia's strategic significance is amplified within these global power changes.¹⁷

The U.S.'s strengthening of its connection with India and China's strong alliance with Pakistan are the key reasons behind the developing competition between the two countries, which is having a substantial impact on the unstable power dynamics in South Asia. As these countries ally with major global powers, this scenario is heightening tensions within the area and may trigger an arms race. Furthermore, the rivalry between the United States and China is unintentionally drawing neighboring nations like Pakistan and India into their geopolitical disputes, which affects their economic stability. South Asian nations must emphasize regional stability, use effective diplomacy, and participate in international discussions to negotiate these complex dynamics.¹⁸

Pakistan is being greatly impacted by the growing competition between Beijing and Washington, particularly in its relations with India. The long-standing hostility between New Delhi and Islamabad is getting worse due to the U.S. and India's growing cooperation, which aims to contain China. This might lead to an arms race and improve both countries' military might. Furthermore, this rivalry makes it less likely that the United States and China will successfully work together to resolve issues that may arise from the escalating war between India and Pakistan. Pakistan has the opportunity to strengthen its stance against India without resorting to cross-border militancy thanks to the ongoing border issues between China and India in eastern Ladakh in 2019. However, this scenario heightens India's concerns

¹⁶The effects of US–China competing strategies in Asia-Pacific on India and Pakistan rivalry in the South Asian region,2021: *Asian Journal of Comparative Politics*:: <https://doi.org/10.1177/2057891121102115>

¹⁷ The effects of US–China competing strategies in Asia-Pacific on India and Pakistan rivalry in the South Asian region, 2021, *Asian Journal of Comparative Politics* ,: <https://doi.org/10.1177/2057891121102115>

¹⁸ The U.S.-China Strategic Rivalry and its Implications for Pakistan, December 1, 2020, *Geopolitics of the Indo-Pacific Project*

about the potential for simultaneous hostilities with China and Pakistan, which may worsen the already strained ties between the two countries. Moreover, while Washington acknowledges that these border issues present an opportunity to strengthen ties with India, India's economic difficulties and the requirement to devote military resources to its border with China limit its capacity to participate fully in the United States' Indo-Pacific strategy. Pakistan may suffer greatly from the possible extension of Washington's Indo-Pacific strategy to support India in its land-based confrontations with China. While a sudden change in U.S. policy seems unlikely, recent moves such as the U.S.-India 2+2 Dialogue and the agreements to supply India with cutting-edge missile and geospatial intelligence have alarmed Pakistan. Pakistan is concerned that these actions, together with a major military accord inked during President Trump's 2020 visit to India, could tip the regional power balance in India's favor.¹⁹

With India, the US has strengthened its strategic alliance to challenge China's hegemony in the area. The tensions between Pakistan and India have already been heightened by this action, with India using American assistance to economically isolate Pakistan by blocking plans to build regional connectivity. Pakistan feels under pressure to keep up with India's military buildup, which is being encouraged by the US, due to the US-China competition. The two nuclear-armed countries are now engaged in an arms race as a result of this circumstance.²⁰

South Asia's economic unification has been hampered by the US-China competition. Pakistan has been left out of regional initiatives like SAARC by India, which has instead focused on indirect connection projects like the India-Myanmar-Thailand Corridor, which purposefully skips Pakistan. Pakistan and other South Asian nations are unable to realize their full geoeconomics potential due to the lack of regional economic integration. As a result, compared to other

regions, South Asia has substantially less intraregional commerce.

In the case of a new cold war provoked by Beijing and Washington competition, Pakistan, which once sided with the USA and operated as a proxy in Afghanistan, causing enormous turbulence there, has announced that it will not align with any bloc. The consequences Pakistan faced by supporting the US during the previous Cold War have an impact on this decision. Now that the USA and India have forged a new alliance, the circumstances have changed. India has benefited greatly from this relationship in several ways, including having access to cutting-edge weapons and the ability to launch weapons into space. Furthermore, the Indo-US nuclear accord has changed the dynamics of the area and established India as a vital security supplier to the United States... Pakistan may be exposed to additional dangers in the future due to the region's possible vulnerabilities resulting from China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI)²¹

Pakistan's foreign policy on the way to Afghanistan can be influenced by its relationship with the US and China in several ways. Pakistan is a key participant in the Chinese Belt and road initiative through the CPEC.²² enhanced economic ties through these projects could lead Pakistan to align its foreign policy more closely with Chinese interests, including China's stance on Afghanistan.

Historically us has been a significant donor to Pakistan. However, if Pakistan is seen as tilting more towards China, it could lead to a reevaluation of its relationship with the US, which could affect US support and influence on Pakistan's foreign policy decisions, including those regarding Afghanistan. Following the conclusion of its prolonged military presence in Afghanistan in 2021 with the evacuation of troops, the US turned its attention to East Asia to counter China's expanding influence and alter the dynamics of the region. The US's reduced level of active involvement in Afghanistan has provided

¹⁹ The U.S.-China Strategic Rivalry and its Implications for Pakistan, December 1, 2020, Geopolitics of the Indo-Pacific Project

²⁰ Dawna newspaper, dr Raashid 2022

²¹ Warisha Rashid. US-CHINA Competition: Implications for The South Asian Strategic

Stability. Science Open Preprints. 2022. DOI: 10.14293/S2199-1006.1.SOR-PPBZJYI.v1

²² The effects of US-China competing strategies in Asia-Pacific on India and Pakistan rivalry in the South Asian region, 2022, Volume 7, Issue 4
<https://doi.org/10.1177/20578911211021>

Pakistan with the chance to review its foreign strategy. Pakistan may become more reliant on China for security and economic assurances as the US's dependence on Pakistan to bring about stability in Afghanistan declines. Through the Belt and Road Initiative and particularly the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor, China has invested heavily in Pakistan's infrastructure and economy. Given the proximity of these projects and the possibility of cross-border effects of Afghan instability on investment zones, the stability of Afghanistan is critical to their safety and success. To better align itself with Chinese regional objectives, Pakistan may thus design its foreign policy to ensure a stable Afghanistan that may be involved in upcoming economic initiatives under the BRI.

Pakistan is still trying to strike a strategic balance between the US and China by maintaining positive ties with both countries to maximize the advantages in terms of financial support, military aid, and diplomatic support. This includes working together with China on economic ventures like the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) and the US on counterterrorism efforts. This balance is probably reflected in Pakistan's approach to Afghanistan, which aims to promote a political settlement that serves the interests of China and the US in the area.²³ The US-China competition has an impact on Pakistan's security concerns. While Pakistan's goal of keeping Afghanistan from serving as a base for terrorists who could destabilize both Pakistan and the region as a whole is aligned with the US's focus on counterterrorism, Pakistan may find itself gradually reliant on China for security cooperation and assurance as a result of the US's strategic shift towards Asia. To safeguard its investments, China has a stake in regional stability, which influences this tendency as well.

²³ Pak-China-US Triangle vis-à-vis Soviet Union in Afghan War, 2014, *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*: 10.5901/mjss. 2014.v5n20p2192

²⁴ India in the Emergent Multipolar World Order: Dynamics and Strategic Challenges, 2022, *India Quarterly: A Journal of International Affairs* <https://doi.org/10.1177/0974928419901187>

Pakistan has difficulties in managing the US-China rivalry on a diplomatic level. For instance, China might anticipate that Pakistan will support its foreign policy endeavors, such as those connected to the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), even though these may be at odds with US objectives.²⁴

However, the US can also anticipate that Pakistan to back its stances on matters on which it is opposed. One of the most important components of China's Belt and Road Initiative is the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC), which serves as an example of the delicate balance Pakistan must maintain. China agrees to support economic projects in Pakistan in exchange for CPEC, which gives China access to the Middle East and Africa through Gwadar Port.²⁵

Pakistan's economy can be strengthened and its energy shortages can be addressed by the development projects linked to the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC). Pakistan therefore has good geopolitical and economic reasons to maintain tight ties with China.²⁶ economic reasons to maintain tight ties with China. The broader US-China rivalry also affects Pakistan's relations with Iran. Due to differences over Iran's nuclear program, the US and Iran have had tense relations that have resulted in sanctions and diplomatic tensions. Consequently, Pakistan exercises caution while interacting with Iran, taking into account possible US retaliation as well as its desire to maintain a healthy balance between these two formidable international rivals.²⁷ Pakistan must take into account the US's stance towards Iran even if it has an interest in forging closer ties with Iran to handle issues related to border security and energy demands. Significant engagement with Iran, especially in ways that would violate US sanctions, could damage Pakistan's standing with Western countries

²⁵ China-Pakistan cooperation on Afghanistan: assessing key interests and implementing strategies, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09512748.2020.1845228>

²⁶ 26 China-Pakistan cooperation on Afghanistan: assessing key interests and implementing strategies, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09512748.2020.1845228>

²⁷ The US-China strategic rivalry and its implications for Pakistan." *Geopolitics of the Indo-Pacific Project* (2020). <http://.researchgate.net>

and, as a result, the financial and military support it receives from them.

On the other hand, Pakistan may improve its role in regional connectivity and trade by aggressively seeking engagement with Iran and taking advantage of its advantageous geographic location and contacts with China and Iran. This is particularly relevant in light of the energy trade, which is essential to China's interests in the Middle East and Africa as well as its energy security.²⁸ To sum up, Pakistan's strategy towards Iran is influenced by the continuous rivalry between the US and China, but it also takes into account its own strategic and economic requirements in an attempt to maintain the support of both giants. The scenarios discussed highlight the difficult geopolitical choices Pakistan must make, and the references given—such as the researcher offer a more thorough comprehension of these nuanced dynamics.²⁹

EVOLUTION OF PAKISTAN FOREIGN POLICY:

In an effort to meet the difficulties of the twenty-first century, Pakistan is difficult to reframe its policy around the ideas of "connectivity" and "balance." The current Cold War dynamics, however, make this endeavor more difficult because Pakistan has to manage its ties with both the US and China, two superpowers that are on the rise. Further complicating Pakistan's foreign policy agenda are the ongoing competition between New Delhi and Islamabad as well as the influence of the US-China-Russia triangular relationship.³⁰ there have been changes in the relationship between Pakistan and the United States, mostly due to the alignment and divergence of their national interests. In spite of this, since Pakistan's independence in 1947, their bilateral relationship has remained favorable, with notable ties

in the areas of social, political, legal, educational, and security. Due to its advantageous geographic and geopolitical location, Pakistan has asked the United States for help in addressing its developmental issues, while the United States has used Pakistani territory for its own purposes.³¹

Over the years, Pakistan's foreign policy has undergone substantial changes and difficulties, frequently impacted by its interactions with powerful nations like China and the United States. Amin (2000) claimed that the period demonstrated Pakistan's lackluster political leadership. In an effort to obtain an advantage over India, the nation joined the South East Asia Treaty Organization and signed the Mutual Defense Assistance Agreement with the United States in 1954. Furthermore, on September 23, 1955, Pakistan signed the Baghdad Pact, which infuriated the Muslim community. As a result of this "Dictated Foreign Policy," Pakistan's diplomatic credibility was called into doubt. Pakistan's foreign policy under Husain Shaheed Suharwardy tried to get better by backing Egypt in the Suez Canal conflict. Pakistan's foreign policy has seen notable changes. Even though the US gave \$29.5 million for this project, the Prime Minister and President Ayub disapproved of it. Pakistan, realizing the weakness in their foreign policy, turned its attention to China, accusing it of aiding separatists in Tibet and in need of support against India. These components draw attention to the intricacies and calculated moves in Pakistan's foreign policy past.³²

Pakistan's foreign policy changed significantly throughout the 1950s and 60s as a result of geopolitical problems and strategic alliances, especially with China and Western powers. According to Sattar (2006), Pakistan's shift toward China unnerved the Western Alliance, which prompted the US to extend further aid to Pakistan, which the

²⁸ "Iran-Pakistan relations: Political and strategic dimensions." *Strategic Analysis* 28, no. 4 (2004): 526-545. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09700160408450157>

²⁹ "The US factor in Pakistan-Iran relations: New dimensions." *J. Pol. Stud.* 24 (2017): 295.

³⁰ Baqai, Huma Naz Siddiqui. "A rearticulation of Pakistan's foreign policy in the wake of the twenty-first century challenges." *Global Pakistan: Pakistan's Role In The International System* (2022): 171-194.

³¹ Asad, M. (2022). Historical Timeline of United States-Pakistan Relations 1947-2020. *International Research Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 1(1), 91-111. Retrieved from <https://irjssh.com/index.php/irjssh/article/view/42>

³² Asad, Muhammad. "Historical Timeline of United States-Pakistan Relations 1947-2020." *International Research Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities* 1, no. 1 (2022): 91-111.

Pakistani government ignored. Pakistan then took a daring stance against the US, the USSR, and India. President Johnson threatened Pakistan with dire consequences if it continued to maintain its distance from China during the 1965 conflict with India, prompting the US to hesitate to provide military support. Pakistan consequently agreed to settle the Kashmir problem by signing the Tashkent Agreement in 1966. Pakistan adopted a low-key strategy and shifted toward bilateralism as a result of the Sino-Indian War. According to Kasuri (2015), during this time, there was a steady change in world politics, which aided Pakistan in regaining political stability after gaining independence. Furthermore, Pakistan's position on the Kashmir dispute was backed by China, led by Premier Liu Shao-chi. These elements draw attention to the intricacies and tactical changes in Pakistan's foreign policy throughout this time.³³ According to Mazhr and Goraya (2013), Pakistan was forced to change its foreign policy and embrace the "War on Terror" as a result of the 9/11 attacks, which allowed Pakistan to re-enter the international political scene after a period of isolation. According to Kasuri (2015), Pakistan was under pressure to stop supporting the Afghans after 9/11, which made it difficult for the country to maintain a balance in its relations with both Afghanistan and the US. Pakistan launched the "Zarb-e-Azb" operation in North Waziristan in response to US pressure, which killed hundreds of civilians and military personnel while successfully removing Taliban hideouts. Pakistan had to follow US orders during this time. According to Sattar (2010), Pakistan has suffered greatly as a result of the US's repeated broken promises and meddling in its internal affairs. Notable examples of this include the fall of East Pakistan in 1971 and the instability that followed the War on Terror. He argues that Pakistan should think about reviewing its foreign policy while taking the interests of major powers into consideration, considering its historical struggles and China's significant backing. According to Markey (2013), Pakistan and the US have never had really bilateral relations since Pakistan

frequently takes a submissive posture and complies with US directives to fight terrorism along its eastern and northwest borders.³⁴

According to Ali (2017), during this period, the connection between China and Pakistan strengthened and endured, earning the moniker "All Weather Good Friendship." Relations significantly improved during this time, as evidenced by Pakistani President Asif Ali Zardari's official meeting to China. Zardari and Chinese Premier Xi Jinping had lengthy discussions about the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor project during this visit. The author suggests that worries about China's actions being directed against lessening American power in the region have arisen in the West, especially in the United States, as a result of this growing alliance.

While Pakistan's relations with the US remained problematic, there were notable advances in Pakistan's relations with India during the PML-N government.

According to Kasuri (2015), there were encouraging changes in Pakistan-India ties during the PML-N administration. The Indian Prime Minister visited Pakistan in 2015 and 2016, indicating advancements for both countries. However, Kasuri also notes that there were difficulties in the US-Pakistan relationship as a result of numerous terrorist attacks in Pakistan.

In 2014, tensions peaked when the US Ambassador was contacted by Mr. Sartaj Aziz, the counselor for foreign affairs at the time, to convey concerns over a Pentagon study that connected Pakistan to terrorist activities in Afghanistan and India.

Mazhar & Goraya (2013) concur, stating that improvements in Pakistan-India ties under Nawaz Sharif's leadership were widely praised. The fact that both nations attended the SAARC Summit Conference in Nepal in November 2014 demonstrated the encouraging trend. Furthermore, the unexpected visit to Pakistan by Indian Prime Minister Modi in December 2015 was a major boost to relations between the two countries.

With the China Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC), a massive economic project, China, which is becoming a powerful economic force, is supporting

³³ Boni, Filippo. "Caught between the United States and China: Critical junctures in Pakistan's foreign policy." In Routledge handbook on South Asian foreign policy, pp. 313-325. Routledge, 2021.

³⁴ Boni, Filippo. "Caught between the United States and China: Critical junctures in Pakistan's foreign policy." In Routledge handbook on South Asian foreign policy, pp. 313-325. Routledge, 2021.

Pakistan. This program has raised concerns in the US and is an essential component of China's massive "One Belt One Road" (OBOR) project. The US interprets the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) as a change in Pakistan's foreign policy and sees it as a calculated move by China to weaken US influence in the area. Pakistan has been placed on the Financial Action Task Force's "Grey List" due to its significant debt load and the absence of concrete assistance from its partners. Pakistan is currently dealing with security concerns in Baluchistan and tensions with India along its eastern borders. Furthermore, permeable northwest borders have increased its vigilance since 2000. In addition, Pakistan and Iran have tense relations since Iran maintains strong ties with India.

Pakistan is in a situation where it needs to depend on friends like China for real economic support, especially through programs like the China Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC). With Prime Minister Imran Khan attempting to mediate disputes between Saudi Arabia and Iran, Pakistan likewise hopes to strengthen its ties with Iran. Pakistan is also actively involved in mediating talks between the United States and the Taliban in Afghanistan.³⁵

The variables affecting bilateral ties between China and Pakistan have changed dramatically in recent years. China and Pakistan are now more closely connected as a result of China's engagement in regional geostrategic concerns like the peace process in Afghanistan and those pertaining to India. Despite China's attempts to use diplomacy to defuse the tensions with India, mistrust still exists. Despite this, Pakistan-China cooperation now includes development and trade-focused engagement in addition to diplomatic and defense-focused cooperation. It is stressed, although, that China cannot completely replace the US and Pakistan, and Islamabad must continue to cooperate with both nations in order to achieve its foreign policy objectives.³⁶

Conclusion:

The 21st-century global geopolitics is characterized by the rising competition between Beijing and Washington. For nations like Pakistan, which are positioned at the crossroads of important power dynamics, this competition has enormous consequences. The US and China's strategic maneuvers are having an increasing impact on Pakistan's foreign policy, especially about its relations with its neighbors, Afghanistan, Iran, and India.

Tensions between Pakistan and India have increased as a result of the US-China competition since both nations have allied with powerful nations to strengthen their armed forces. Pakistan is facing pressure to manage these intricate dynamics while pursuing positive relations with other countries and preserving its long-standing ties with China. Pakistan's foreign policy toward Afghanistan is influenced by the geopolitical rivalry between the US and China as it attempts to strike a balance between security considerations and economic goals, particularly through programs like the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC).

Recommendation:

Pakistan must maintain a delicate balance between China and the US, and use its relations with both nations to maximize aid in the form of cash, military support, and diplomatic backing. It should simultaneously concentrate on establishing stability in the area by actively engaging in dialogue with its neighbors and bringing its economy closer to theirs. Participating in international discussions is also crucial for Pakistan. Furthermore, Pakistan must maintain friendly relations with other nations, such as Iran, to avoid becoming overly dependent on any one nation. Pakistan will be able to manage the intricate dynamics surrounding it and maintain stability and prosperity in this way.

³⁵ Darabu, Fauzia, and Sayeda Daud. "New Era in Pakistan's Foreign Policy: Problems and Prospects." *Pakistan Journal of International Affairs* 4, no. 1 (2021).

³⁶ Muhammad Faisal *Strategic Studies*, Vol. 40, No. 2 (Summer 2020), pp. 23-44 (22 pages)
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